

WORLD EXPERIENCE OF LEGAL REGULATION OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY AND THE POSSIBILITY OF ITS APPLICATION IN UKRAINE

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SUMMARY

Articolul explorează fundamentele reglementării legale a activităților de investiții din țările lumii, analizează starea actuală a cadrului juridic care reglementează starea și dezvoltarea activităților de investiții din țările menționate mai sus. A fost efectuată analiza experienței internaționale în reglementarea juridică a activităților de investiții ale țărilor străine, a fost luată în considerare experiența străină în sistematizarea legislației investiționale, în special prin codificare și posibilitatea implementării acesteia în Ucraina.

Problem statement The legal framework of Ukraine regulating the state of investment activity, stages of the investment process and public administration relations in the field of investment activity constitute a large system of laws and bylaws regulating the state and development of investment activity in Ukraine. However, the current legislation governing the country's activities in the above area is imperfect, due to the large array of conflicts and gaps, which determines the relevance of this study.

Study and analysis of successful international experience in improving investment legislation and its implementation in Ukraine, will develop a transparent, stable, clearly systematized system of regulations in this area and will improve the investment climate in Ukraine, attract foreign investment and create new and effective mechanisms public administration of investment processes.

Analysis of recent research and publications: Issues of updating and improving investment legislation have been considered in the works of many Ukrainian scholars. The urgency of the problem of systematization of investment legislation is explained by a number of scientific publications, the purpose of which is to substantiate the feasibility of adopting the Investment Code of Ukraine. Among the main works are the works of V. Poedynok, V. Nagrebelny and others.

However, the issue of systematization and regulation of national legislation in the field of investment remains relevant today and requires further study and implementation.

The purpose of the article is to study the current state of the regulatory framework governing investment activities of foreign countries, analysis of the experience of systematization of investment legislation in some countries and the possibility of its implementation in national investment legislation.

Presentation of the main material: An important tool and mechanism for effective investment activities, in particular in the process of attracting foreign investment is the availability of modern and existing regulatory framework that meets European standards. In order to implement the best world practices of legal regulation in the national investment legislation, it is necessary to study and study in detail the foreign experience of the world's leading countries in this field.

Considering the investment legislation of Germany, it should be noted that in this country there is no single legislative act governing the implementation of investment activities, in particular in the field of attracting foreign investment

The main regulations in the field of investment activities are:

- Law "On Foreign Economic Relations"
- Law "On Foreign Trade and Payments"
- Resolution "On Foreign Trade and Payments".

The provisions of the Law on Foreign Economic Relations are the basis for regulating and conducting foreign exchange transactions and investments.

The Law on Foreign Trade and Payments is the legal basis for controlling foreign investment. The procedure for reviewing investments is regulated by the Administrative Code, which contains rules for the legal protection of investment control.

The rules of the regulation on foreign trade and payments regulate the procedure for conducting an inspection of any investor who is not a citizen of the European Union or a country that is not a member of the European Free Trade Association. Investment activities in France are governed by the provisions of the Treaty of Rome and EU law. France has signed bilateral investment agreements (BITs) with 95 countries.

French DIDs usually include the following:

- Fair and equal treatment (no less favorable than that provided to domestic investors or the greatest assistance to investors from third countries); European vector of economic development;
- Restrictions on expropriation of investments, as well as requirements that, in case of expropriation, will be compensated promptly and in adequate amounts;
- Free transfers;
- Ability to resolve disputes through mandatory international arbitration. [2].

Japan's national legislation in the field of investment activities consists of a number of regulations governing the import of investments and various measures to attract foreign capital.

Most of the legislation was adopted in the post-war period and is in force with significant amendments to date. Legal regulation of investment activity is carried out by laws and international agreements.

Among the main legal acts regulating the investment sphere in Japan are the following:

- Law “On Foreign Currency and Foreign Trade;
- Opening of the Cabinet of Ministers for Foreign Direct Investment;
- Order on domestic direct investment;
- International investment agreements with Georgia, Ivory Coast, Morocco and Argentina;
- Agreements with investment regulations with Great Britain and EU countries.

Of interest is the legal regulation of investment activities in the United States of America, where the key legal act in this area is the Law on Foreign Investment and National Security, which was adopted in 2007. This law regulates the procedure for controlling the admission of foreign capital in the field related to national security. This law defines the concepts of investment agreements that must be reviewed by the Security Committee.

It should be noted that in some countries around the world, investment legislation is codified. In world practice, there are examples of the adoption of the investment code. Côte d’Ivoire, Algeria, Gabon, Guinea, Morocco, Niger, Somalia and others were among the first to adopt an investment code. [1].

In particular, the Investment Code of the Republic of Côte d’Ivoire was adopted and enacted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of 07.06.2012 №487.

The provisions of the Code apply to all foreign and national investors - individuals and legal entities. At the same time, foreign investors are guaranteed similar conditions provided to local investors, as well as free access to the purchase of freely convertible currency required for settlements with foreign suppliers [3].

In accordance with the provisions of this code, the republic guarantees the free export of capital by the investor, but subject to the proper fulfillment of tax obligations to the budget.

Foreign employees of the investor are free to transfer abroad their wages and other payments due to them in compliance with the current rules of currency regulation [3].

The authorities of the republic guarantee:

- protection of tangible and intangible rights belonging to the investor on private property rights;
- free appointment of members of the boards of directors, general directors and other managers of the company.

The state facilitates the unimpeded receipt of work visas and residence permits for shareholders of the investor's company, as well as employees who travel to Côte d'Ivoire. Foreign investors are guaranteed access to a fair trial in the event of disputes with the state that cannot be resolved through negotiations. Investors have the right to settle disputes under the arbitration mechanisms provided for in the New York Convention of March 18, 1965. The investor is obliged to comply with Ivorian law, including in the field of labor protection (according to the requirements of ISO 26 000) and the environment. Investment projects must be declared to the Investment Commissioner, who registers them within two working days. [3].

Having analyzed these legislative acts in detail, it should be noted that although they do not aim at comprehensive legal regulation of the entire array of investment relations, but at the same time form a holistic, harmonious system of investment legislation.

Ukraine has also tried to adopt an investment code aimed at protecting the rights and legitimate interests of participants in investment relations and ensuring an attractive investment environment in the country, but at present, they have remained only at the level of the bill.

Conclusions and proposals: Given all the above, it must be concluded that in developed countries, the sources of investment law are a set of regulations governing the legal regulation of investment activities, the rules of which establish state guarantees for foreign investment, regulate the procedure and conditions investment activities and ensure proper implementation of foreign investors' tasks. However, despite the array of legislation governing investment, in most countries, as in Ukraine, there is no single piece of legislation (investment code) that regulates investment activities. In particular, the investment activities of these countries are regulated by a group of legislative acts governing economic, labor, tax and administrative relations, the rules of which contradict each other, which greatly complicates the procedure for attracting investment to the economy of these countries.

Summarizing all the above, we consider it appropriate to implement in Ukrainian investment legislation the successful world experience of systematization of regulations by bringing the current regulatory framework of Ukraine in the field of investment to international standards and adopt a single codified act, which would greatly facilitate the investment process. investment climate of the country and provide security guarantees for foreign investors.

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